

Forced convection heat transfer performance of the turbulent flow in a triangular channel of nanofluid (Al_2O_3 -water) and hybrid nanofluid (Al_2O_3 - SiO_2 -water)

Imen Meriem ¹, Rahima Benchabi ²

¹ LEAP Laboratory, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of the Brothers Mentouri Constantine 1, 25000, Algeria,

² LEAP Laboratory, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of the Brothers Mentouri Constantine 1, 25000, Algeria,

*Corresponding author(s). Imen Meriem

Contributing authors: Rahima Benchabi

Abstract

In this paper, Al_2O_3 - SiO_2 -water hybrid nanofluid and Al_2O_3 -water nanofluid with 3% volume fraction were studied for their flow and heat transfer characteristics inside a triangular channel. In order to study the hybrid nanofluid, many ratios in percent volume of alumina (Al_2O_3) and silicon dioxide (SiO_2) in water (10:90, 20:80, 30:70, 40:60, 50:50) were taken. Both the top and bottom of the corrugated ducts were kept at a constant temperature. The particle diameter in this study is 30 nm, and Reynolds numbers fall between 1000 and 5000. Governing equations are solved using the SIMPLE (Semi-implicit method for pressure-linked Equations) algorithm. The obtained findings show that: the confidence in the numerical model's performance was guaranteed by the results of the experimental and numerical models agreeing well, the Nusselt number grows in tandem with the Reynolds number for mono and hybrid nanofluids; nevertheless, the coefficient of friction reduces as the Reynolds number rises. Concerning this friction coefficient, hybrid and mono nanofluids are identical. The hybrid nanofluid with the percentage ratio (10:90) performs the best in terms of convective transfer, while the hybrid nanofluid with the percentage ratio (50:50) performs the worst, the total entropy, the bejan number, and the entropy resulting from heat transfer all decrease as the Reynolds number rises; on the other hand, the entropy due to viscous increases. Compared to mono nanofluids, hybrid nanofluids have a greater pressure drop. Two correlations were established using the investigation's numerical findings.

Keywords — Heat Transfer, Forced Convection, Corrugated Channel, Nanofluid, Hybrid Nanofluid.

I. INTRODUCTION

Heat transfer by forced convection still has its value in industry and in all areas requiring convective heat transfer such as heat exchangers used in climate engineering, the chemical industry or the food and petroleum industries. The intensification of this convective heat transfer is the objective of researchers in this field over the last decade. According to previous studies, the improvement of heat transfer by convection depends mainly on the enhancement of the thermal conductivity of the nanofluid, the density concentrations of the nanoparticles scattered throughout the base liquid, the velocity or flow regime of the nanofluid and also the thermal conductivity of the nanoparticles. In order to increase the thermal conductivity of a nanofluid, the researchers discover a novel improved nanofluid containing two kinds of nanoparticles, called a hybrid nanofluid, it is made by putting different nanoparticles in suspension in the form of nanometric size composite. The use of hybrid nanofluids for thermal intensification is the aim of this study.

Many studies have been directed towards this line of research such as:

R. Benchabi and A. Lanani [1] carried out a numerical investigation of incompressible turbulent flow in two dimensions in a channel that mimics a heat exchanger with corrugated plates and involves heat transfer. Their research made it possible to observe how the Reynolds number affects the dynamic and thermal field as well as the rate of heat transfer, and that the local Nusselt number achieves its highest values in regions with high velocity and those that correspond to fluid re-bonding points. The average Nusselt numbers are superior to the smooth channel's and rise as the Reynolds number does. As the Reynolds number rises, the friction coefficient falls.

K. Heguehoug Benkara and R. Benchabi [2] performed a numerical investigation of a heat transfer in a two-dimensional turbulent flow in a corrugated channel employing Al_2O_3 nanoparticles with a volume percentage of 3% dispersed in water and particle diameter of 30 nm, they discovered that a higher Reynolds number results in a higher average Nusselt and a lower friction coefficient. As Reynolds increases, the Bejan number and transfer entropy produced in the fluid moving through the channel both drop, but friction increases. Furthermore, the use of an Al_2O_3 /water nanofluid provides superior heat transfer than pure water.

I. Meriem and R. Benchabi [3] investigated the characteristics of copper oxide (CuO), SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 nanoparticles in terms of flow and heat transfer with a 5% volume percentage in a straight and wavy channel with various forms (square, triangle, and trapezoidal), utilizing ethylene glycol, glycerin, and water as base fluids. According to their findings, the average

Nusselt number rises and the friction factor falls as the Reynolds number rises. Furthermore, compared to square, triangular, and straight channels, the corrugated trapezoidal channel provides better convective heat transfer, furthermore, whereas the entropy generated by friction rises as the Reynolds number rises, the entropy generated by heat transfer and the total entropy creation fall as the Reynolds number rises. The Bejan number falls as the Reynolds number rises. Furthermore, SiO₂-glycerin nanofluid enhances heat transfer more than any other base fluid. Compared to the cylindrical shape, the spherical shape provides the best convective heat transmission performance. Also, two correlations were established using the study's numerical results.

B.Takabi et al [4] examined numerically the laminar forced convection of several working fluids, such as pure water, in a circular tube that is heated evenly, both an Al₂O₃ and copper (Cu) nanoparticle hybrid solution in water and a nanofluid (Al₂O₃ nanoparticles dissolved in water) with varying volume concentrations are achieved. They discovered that, compared to nanofluid and pure water, the use of hybrid suspension raises the rate of heat transfer for every Reynolds number under study. Even so, the existence of nanoparticles has a negative impact on the shear stress of the walls and the friction factor. In hybrid suspension, nevertheless, the entire Nusselt number's average increase is 7.20%, but the friction factor has increased by 10.94% on average.

S. Suresh et al [5] created hybrid Al₂O₃-Cu particles using a hydrogen reduction process from a powdered combination of CuO and Al₂O₃ in weight proportions of 90%:10% that were acquired through chemical synthesis. They then created Al₂O₃-Cu/water hybrid nanofluids with volume contents ranging from 0.1% to 2% by dispersing the powdered nanocomposite in deionized water. The experimental findings showed that when the nanoparticles' volume concentration rises, so do the created hybrid nanofluids' thermal conductivity and viscosity. For a volume concentration of 2%, a maximum improvement of 12,11% was found in the experimental measurement of heat conductivity, indicating that the increase in viscosity is far larger than the increase in thermal conductivity.

J. Sarkar et al [6] compiled a summary of latest studies on the creation of hybrid nanofluids, features of heat transfer and pressure drop, possible applications thermophysical, properties and difficulties. The analysis found that good hybridization can make hybrid nanofluids hold great promise for enhancing heat transfer. Nonetheless, to address challenges, more research is required in the areas of preparedness and applications, characterization and stability.

L. Syam Sundar et al [7] reviewed how hybrid nanoparticles are made, thermal properties, heat transfer, friction factor, the creation of hybrid nanofluids, and Nusselt number and the friction

factor correlations that are already accessible. This study also shows that hybrid nanofluids are more efficient heat transfer fluids than traditional fluids or simple nanoparticle-based nanofluids. However, Still, there is a lack of comprehension of the mechanisms underlying improved heat transfer in hybrid nanofluids, necessitating a significant amount of study.

G. Humnic and A. Humnic [8] reviewed the results of recent research on the thermophysical properties (thermal conductivity, viscosity, specific heat and density) and flow and heat transfer characteristics of hybrid nanofluids used in various heat exchangers. According to the numerical and experimental results presented in this study, working fluids known as hybrid nanofluids have the potential to significantly improve heat transfer in heat exchangers. However, further research is needed to investigate the different combinations of hybrid nanoparticles, their mixing ratios, methods for improving heat transfer and the stability of hybrid nanofluids.

K.A. Hamid et al [9] used forced convection heat transmission of hybrid nanofluids (at a volume concentration of 1.0%) to experimentally analyze the Nusselt number and heat transfer coefficient at three mixing ratios of titanium dioxide (TiO_2) with SiO_2 (50:50, 20:80, and 80:20) water- ethylene glycol (EG) combination. The experiment was carried out in a simple tube with a constant heat flux of 7955 W/m^2 and a 30°C working temperature. They discovered that the average improvement in the Nusselt number and heat transfer coefficient was 9.0–17.8% and 13.6–29.7%, respectively; the 20:80 $\text{TiO}_2/\text{SiO}_2$ ratio showed to be the optimal ratio for achieving maximum improvement in Nusselt number and heat transfer coefficient, at a 50:50 ratio, about twice as much pressure was dropped by the hybrid nanofluid as by the base fluid. The hybrid nanofluid is ideal for cooling system applications due to a modest improvement in the friction factor of 1.03 times. Then, because of the major enhancement in heat transfer but the smallest rise in friction factor, a $\text{TiO}_2\text{-SiO}_2$ nanofluid at a ratio of 20:80 is suggested.

N.S.M. Sahid et al [10] synthesized hybrid nanofluids with a particle size of 21 nm TiO_2 and a 10–30 nm zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticle in a combination of water and ethylene glycol and the proportion of this base fluid (water: EG) in order to conduct an experimental study on the stability and properties of hybrid nanofluids with different volume concentrations between 0.1% and 1.5%. The nanoparticles were suspended in different ratios of TiO_2 : ZnO (80:20, 70:30 and 90:10). The findings demonstrated that the viscosity and thermal conductivity of hybrid nanofluids were significantly affected by temperature, water-EG as the base fluid, and hybrid nanofluid concentration.

M. Amiri et al [11] carried out a study where they synthesized and characterized $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Cu}$ nanocomposites, as well as measuring and reporting $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Cu/EG}$ and $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Cu/water}$ nanofluids' thermal conductivity. Its findings show that by chemically depositing a little quantity of Cu onto the SiO_2 surface, the thermal conductivity of the base fluid is greatly

raised, the water's thermal conductivity can be increased to 11% with the water nanofluid containing less than 1% of modified nanocomposites, while EG with the same amount of nanoparticles increased its thermal conductivity by about 11.5% (at 25°C). The fact that this form of nanofluid produces particles with a density similar to SiO₂ but a copper-like thermal effect is one of the most significant aspects of this research.

M.F. Nabil et al [12] conducted experimental effort focuses on TiO₂-SiO₂ nanofluids' dynamic viscosity and thermal conductivity in a 60:40 water and EG mixture at volume percentages spanning from 0.5% to 3.0%, were studied in a temperature range of 30 to 80 °C. The results of the work show that: TiO₂-SiO₂ nanofluids' thermal conductivity rose by up to 22.8% with increases in nanoparticle volume concentration and temperature, temperature and concentration of TiO₂-SiO₂ nanofluids had an effect on their viscosity, for concentrations of more than 1.5% and within the studied temperature range, the properties enhancement ratio suggests that heat transport would be aided by TiO₂-SiO₂ nanofluids. Finally, the researchers devised a new correlation between TiO₂-SiO₂ nanofluids' thermal conductivity and dynamic viscosity that has been proven to be accurate.

M. Benkhedda et al [13] investigated laminar mixed convection numerically in a horizontal ring containing an TiO₂/water nanofluid and an Ag-TiO₂/water hybrid nanofluid. The numerical simulations are run for a range of Grashof numbers (between 10⁵ and 10⁶) and nanoparticle volume fractions (between 0 and 8%). The findings indicate that for every Grashof number under study, as Grashof number and the volume fraction rise, thus, do the bulk temperature and the local and average Nusselt values. Instead of utilizing a TiO₂/water nanofluid comparable to this, use a hybrid Silver (Ag)-TiO₂/water nanofluid, because the heat transfer is significantly improved. In addition, by using the numerical results they were able to collect, they were able to establish two new correlations. The findings show that there is a strong link between the correlation data and the numerical data. For both hybrid nanofluid an nanofluid, the maximum inaccuracy was approximately 4.7% and 2.5%, respectively.

A.I. Ramadhan et al [14] investigated both numerically and experimentally in a simple tube, the convective heat transfer of TiO₂-SiO₂ nanoparticles dispersed throughout water/EG, under a wall heat flow constant with volume concentrations of 1, 2, and 3%, Reynolds number ranges from 2900 to 11,200. They discussed how heat transfer coefficients and friction factors are affected by hybrid nanofluids. The findings demonstrate that, in both numerical and experimental cases, the greatest Nusselt and friction factor was discovered in hybrid nanofluids with a volume concentration of 3%; 2% and 1%; came next, heat transfer in plain tubes increases with Reynolds number. The Nusselt number average deviation for the volume concentrations of 1, 2, and 3% in this study was determined to be 8.8, 8.9, and 7.9% when

comparing the experimental and numerical data, for volume concentrations of 1, 2, and 3%, the average friction factor deviance is 4.1, 3.8, and 3.5%, respectively.

M. Tekir et al [15] conducted a numerical analysis of the flow of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Cu}$ /water hybrid nanofluid to improve the heat transfer by forced convection of the base fluid in a square cross-sectional conduit and under a turbulent flow regime (Reynolds number between 10^4 and 10^5) and 5000 W/m^2 of heat flux is continuously applied to the walls, as well as for volume concentrations between 0% and 2%. The findings show that convective heat transfer is significantly enhanced by the hybrid nanofluid (up to 53% enhancement of heat transfer was achieved) and as the Reynolds number, hybrid nanoparticle concentration, and volume concentration increased, so did heat transfer.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

A. Model Description

The triangular channel in Figure 1 represents the basic geometry used in this study. Corrugated channels have a 4 mm amplitude, a 20 mm wavelength and a 200 mm length. They are composed of two corrugated walls with a $H=10 \text{ mm}$ gap between them. There are two adiabatic straight stretches, L_1 and L_2 , upstream and downstream of the channel, respectively. Isothermal heating is used to heat both the upper and below corrugated walls. It is thought to be a fully developed, two-dimensional, Newtonian, steady, and incompressible flow.

Fig. 1 An illustration of the current study :triangular channel.

B. Governing equations

The current model uses the finite volume method to numerically solve the two-dimensional fluid flow and heat transfer problems. It is assumed that the flow is incompressible and Newtonian. [16]

- Continuity equation

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \bar{v}}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (1)$$

- x- momentum equation

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[(\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right] + \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[(\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - \frac{2}{3} \rho_{nf} k \right] + \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right] \quad (2)$$

Where μ_t is the turbulent dynamic viscosity, u is the velocity in the x direction, p is the pressure, μ and ρ_{nf} are the dynamic viscosity and density of the nanofluid, respectively.

- y- momentum equation

$$u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[(\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right] + \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[(\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right] + \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} - \frac{2}{3} \rho_{nf} k \right] \quad (3)$$

Where the velocity in the y direction is indicated by v .

- Energy equation

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\left(\frac{k_{nf}}{c_p} + \frac{\mu_t}{Pr_t} \right) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\left(\frac{k_{nf}}{c_p} + \frac{\mu_t}{Pr_t} \right) \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right] \quad (4)$$

Here, T and k_{nf} stand for temperature and thermal conductivity of the nanofluid, respectively.

To simulate turbulent heat transport and flow characteristics, the Renormalized group k - ϵ turbulence model (RNG) is utilized. [16]

Two more equations are added by the k - ϵ turbulent model and are defined as follows:

- Turbulent kinetic energy (k) equation

$$u \frac{\partial (k)}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial (k)}{\partial y} = (\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k}) \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial k}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial k}{\partial y} \right) \right] + \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} G_k - \epsilon \quad (5)$$

- Rate of dissipation (ϵ) equation

$$u \frac{\partial (\epsilon)}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial (\epsilon)}{\partial y} = (\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\epsilon}) \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial y} \right) \right] + C_{1\epsilon} \frac{\epsilon}{\rho_{nf} k} G_k + C_{2\epsilon} \frac{\epsilon^2}{\rho_{nf} k} G_k \quad (6)$$

Where G_k stands for the turbulence's kinetic energy production rate. These are the turbulent Prandtl numbers for ε and k , respectively: σ_ε and σ_k . The definitions of the constants $C_{2\varepsilon}$ and $C_{1\varepsilon}$ are:

$$C_{2\varepsilon} = 1.68; C_{1\varepsilon} = 1.42; \sigma_\varepsilon = 1.3 \text{ and } \sigma_k = 1.0$$

The turbulent viscosity is expressed as follows:

$$\mu_t = \rho C_\mu \frac{k^2}{\varepsilon} \quad (7)$$

C. Boundary Conditions

Channel inlet:

$$T = T_{in} = 300 \text{ }^\circ\text{K}, u = u_{in}, v = 0, k = k_{in} = \frac{3}{2} (u_{in} I)^2, \varepsilon = \varepsilon_{in} = C_\mu^{3/4} k_{in}^{3/2} (0.07 D_h) \quad (8)$$

Channel outlet:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = 0, \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = 0, \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = 0, \frac{\partial k}{\partial x} = 0, \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (9)$$

Corrugated walls:

$$u = 0, v = 0, k = 0, \varepsilon = 0, T_c = 333 \text{ }^\circ\text{K} \quad (10)$$

- Reynolds number

$$Re = \frac{\rho_f u_f D_h}{\mu_f} \quad (11)$$

The hydraulic diameter, D_h , is computed as follows :

$$D_h = \frac{4S}{P_w} = 2H \quad (12)$$

- Average Nusselt number (Nu) : [17]

$$Nu = \frac{D_h q}{K_f (T_c - T)} = \frac{D_h \Phi}{K_f (T_c - T) S} \quad (13)$$

The friction factor of the nanofluid, denoted by f , is computed as follows:

$$f = \frac{\Delta p}{4 \left(\frac{L}{D_h} \right) \left(\frac{\rho_{nf} u^2}{2} \right)} \quad (14)$$

Where the nanofluid velocity is denoted by u and its density is represented by ρ_{nf} .

D. Thermophysical properties of nanofluids

The density:

A nanofluid's density is expressed as [18]:

$$\rho_{nf} = (1 - \phi)\rho_f + \phi \rho_p \quad (15)$$

In which ρ_p is the density of the solid nanoparticles and ρ_f is the density of base fluid and ϕ is the volume fraction.

Heat capacity:

The nanofluid heat capacity is calculated as [19]:

$$(\rho C_p)_{nf} = (1 - \phi)(\rho C_p)_f + \phi(\rho C_p)_p \quad (16)$$

Where C_{pp} is the heat capacity of the solid nanoparticles and C_{pf} is the heat capacity of the base fluid.

Dynamic viscosity:

The dynamic viscosity effective is given as [20]:

$$\mu_{nf} = \frac{\mu_f}{(1-\phi)^{2.5}} \quad (17)$$

Where μ_f is the base fluid's dynamic viscosity, d_f is the equivalent diameter of a base fluid molecule and d_{np} is the nanoparticle diameter.

Thermal conductivity:

The static conductivity is given by the model of Hamilton and Crosser [21]:

$$K_{static} = k_f \left[\frac{k_p + (n-1)k_f - (n-1)\phi(k_f - k_p)}{k_p (n-1)k_f + \phi(k_f - k_p)} \right] \quad (18)$$

Where n : empirical form factor given by $n = 3/\Psi$ (for spherical particles, $n = 3$ and for cylindrical particles, $n = 6$), with Ψ : Sphericity.

E. Thermophysical properties of hybrids nanofluids

The thermophysical properties of the different types of hybrids nanofluids examined in this study are:

The density:

The density of a hybrid nanofluid is given as [22]:

$$\rho_{hnf} = (1 - \phi_{p1} - \phi_{p2})\rho_f + \phi_{p1}\rho_{p1} + \phi_{p2}\rho_{p2} \quad (19)$$

Where ϕ_{p1} and ρ_{p1} are the volume fraction and the density of the first particle, ϕ_{p2} and ρ_{p2} the volume fraction and the density of the second particle, ρ_f is the density of the base fluid.

Specific heat:

The specific heat of the hybrid nanofluid is expressed as [22]:

$$(\rho c_p)_{hnf} = (1 - \phi_{p1} - \phi_{p2})(\rho c_p)_f + \phi_{p1}\rho_{p1} c_{p1} + \phi_{p2}\rho_{p2} c_{p2} \quad (20)$$

Dynamic viscosity:

The Brinkman model [20] for spherical nanoparticles can be used to determine the hybrid nanofluid's effective dynamic viscosity as

$$\mu_{nf} = \frac{\mu_f}{(1-\phi)^{2.5}} \tag{21}$$

Where: $\phi = \phi_{p1} + \phi_{p2}$ (22)

Thermal conductivity:

According to Ellahi et al. [23] and the Maxwell model [24], the hybrid nanofluid's effective thermal conductivity for spherical particles is:

$$K_{hnf} = k_f \frac{[(\phi_{p1}k_{p1} + \phi_{p2}k_{p2})/\phi] + 2k_f + 2[\phi_{p1}k_{p1} + \phi_{p2}k_{p2}] - 2\phi k_f}{[(\phi_{p1}k_{p1} + \phi_{p2}k_{p2})/\phi] + 2k_f - [\phi_{p1}k_{p1} + \phi_{p2}k_{p2}] + \phi k_f} \tag{23}$$

Table 1 lists the thermophysical properties of the base fluid (water) and the nanoparticles (SiO₂, Al₂O₃) used in this study.

TABLE I
BASE FLUIDS AND NANOPARTICLES THERMOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES at T= 300 k

Thermophysical properties	Water [25]	SiO ₂ [26]	Al ₂ O ₃ [27]
ρ (kg/m ³)	996.5	2220	3600
C _p (J/kg k)	4181	745	765
K(W/m k)	0.613	1.4	36
μ (kg/m s)	0.001	–	–

F. Entropy generation analysis

When thermal and viscous effects are taken into consideration, the local volumetric entropy generation rate can be calculated as [28]:

$$S'''_{g,thermal} = \frac{k + k_t}{T^2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right] \tag{24}$$

$$S'''_{g,viscous} = \frac{\mu + \mu_t}{T} \left\{ 2 \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right] + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right\} \tag{25}$$

$$S'''_g = S'''_{g,thermal} + S'''_{g,viscous} \tag{26}$$

Where K_t and μ_t stand for turbulent thermal conductivity and viscosity, respectively; u, v, and w for the velocity components in the x, y, and z axes.

Bejan number can be expressed as [29]:

$$Be = \frac{S'''_{g,thermal}}{S'''_{g,thermal} + S'''_{g,viscous}} \tag{27}$$

III. CONVERGENCE CRITERIA

In this study, the equations regulating the flow of a nanofluid and hybrid nanofluid in a triangular channel were solved numerically using the finite volume method integrated into the computational fluid dynamic (CFD) code ANSYS-Fluent 14.5. To solve the velocity-pressure coupling problem, Versteeg and Malalasekera's SIMPLE algorithm [30] is employed. The convection and diffusion terms in the governing equations have been discretized using the upwind method with second-order precision; while the gradient and pressure have been discretized using the standard scheme and the least squares cell-based scheme, respectively, with the exception of the energy equation, which has normalized residual values of 10^{-6} , solutions are deemed convergent when they reach 10^{-5} .

IV. MESH SENSITIVITY VALIDATION

A. Mesh sensitivity

Several meshes were tested on the triangular geometry of Naphon [31] to see the effect of the number of nodes on the solution (local Nusselt number and skin friction coefficient) at $Re=730$ as depicted in Figure 2, it is discovered that a grid-independent solution is guaranteed at grid size 51801.

(b)

Fig. 2 Test of grid independence (a) local Nusselt number (b) skin friction coefficient.

B. Model validation

To verify the mathematical model and numerical approach employed in the research: The hybrid nanofluid ($\text{TiO}_2\text{-SiO}_2/\text{water-EG}$) with percentage ratios [(20:80)/(60:40)] flow results in a straight channel are compared with the experimental results of Hamid et al [32] in terms of Nusselt number and the skin friction coefficient. As seen in Figure 3, there is a good agreement and this indicates the accuracy of the numerical model used.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3 Validation of the results of this study with those of Hamid et al [32] (a) Nu vs Re (b) skin friction coefficient vs Re.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this subsection, a comparison between an Al_2O_3 -water nanofluid and two of the Al_2O_3 - SiO_2 -water hybrid nanofluids [(10:90) and (50:50)] with a volume fraction (ϕ) equal to 0.03 in order to see the convective heat transfer performance of a hybrid nanofluid compared to another mono nanofluid as illustrated in Figure 4. As it is visible, the Nusselt increases with the increase of Reynolds for both types of nanofluids (mono and hybrid) and the hybrid nanofluids (10:90, 50:50) transfer heat by convection better than the Al_2O_3 -water even if adding a little amount of SiO_2 to the Al_2O_3 -water makes the difference and improves the convective heat transfer. A comparison between volume percentage ratios of Al_2O_3 - SiO_2 in water with a volume fraction equal to 0.03 was carried out in order to show the best ratio between them in terms of convective heat transfer. As it is clear in Figure 5 (a) and (b), the volume percent ratio (10:90) has the highest Nusselt number in any studied Reynolds number range, followed by the ratio (20:80), (30:70), (40:60), and finally (50:50).

Fig. 4 Variation of the Average Nusselt number as a function of Reynolds number for hybrid nanofluids Al₂O₃-SiO₂-water [(10:90), (50:50)] and nanofluid Al₂O₃-water ($\phi = 0.03$).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5 Variation of the Average Nusselt number as a function of Reynolds number for hybrid nanofluids Al₂O₃-SiO₂-water [(10:90), (20:80), (30:70), (40:60), (50:50)] ($\phi = 0.03$).

As it is well known that friction is an essential physical phenomenon in the flows of nanofluids (mono or hybrid) and occurs in parallel with a heat transfer in the pipes, the figure 6 shows the variation of friction coefficient as a function of Reynolds number and the results presented in this figure show that there is no difference even if it was small in coefficient of friction, that is to say the same value of coefficient of friction in the same Reynolds number for all hybrid nanofluids Al₂O₃-SiO₂-water (10:90, 20:80, 30:70, 40:60, 50:50) and the mono nanofluid Al₂O₃-water.

Fig. 6 Friction factor variation in line with Reynolds number for nanofluid and different hybrid nanofluids ($\phi = 0.03$).

A pressure drop accompanied by the heat transfer during the flow and this is due to the friction of the nanofluid with the walls of the channel and also to the friction of the nanofluid on itself. This is what is called shear stresses; this leads to a pressure loss. The results of the pressure drop as a function of Reynolds number are shown in Figure 7. It is evident that hybrid nanofluids experience a greater pressure drop than mono nanofluids.

Fig. 7 variation of pressure drop as a function of Reynolds number for nanofluid and various hybrids nanofluid ($\phi = 0.03$).

A. Effect of Entropy Generation

A. Bejan [33,34] started the study of entropy generation and believes that viscous and thermal mechanisms, involving temperature and velocity gradients, promote the generation of entropy of a fluid's flow in a forced and laminar convection regime. The key finding from the researchers' work on the idea of entropy generation in convective heat transfer systems is that fluid friction and heat transfer are the primary causes of entropy generation. We examined the variations in entropy generation brought on by heat transport (Figure 8 (a)), friction in this subsection Figure 8 (b) and total entropy generation Figure 8 (c) for a Al_2O_3 -water nanofluid and Al_2O_3 - SiO_2 -water hybrid nanofluid flow with $\varnothing = 0.03$ inside the triangular channel as a function of Reynolds number. As the Reynolds number rises, it is also observed that entropy due to heat transfer decreases because the temperature gradient within whether it is nanofluid or hybrid nanofluid decreases with increasing velocity. In contrast, entropy due to friction increases as the Reynolds number rises because of a slight increase in the velocity gradient within the nanofluid with each increase in velocity. Since this increase is negligible in comparison to the decrease in entropy production due to heat transfer, total entropy production also decreases as the Reynolds number rises. It has been noted that the reduction in entropy caused by transfer is less for a hybrid nanofluid than for a nanofluid. Also, for a hybrid nanofluid, the decrease in entropy generation due to transfer along the studied Reynolds number interval is less than for a nanofluid and that for a hybrid nanofluid the increase in entropy generation due to friction along the studied Reynolds number interval is significant than a nanofluid. This last remark is applied on the total entropy generation and the Bejan number presented in Figure 8 (d). In addition, as the Reynolds number rises, the Bejan number falls, as shown in Figure 8 (d). This indicates that heat effects outweigh viscous effects, and with reference to equation (27).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8 (a) Variation of the entropy generation due to heat transfer effects (b) Variation of the entropy generation due to friction (c) Total entropy generation variation (d) Bejan Reynolds number in a triangular channel.

B. Development of a new Correlations of Nusselt number

Recent years have seen the publication of some correlations for estimating the Nu number for nanofluids and their hybrids [35, 36]. These novel correlations are exclusively applicable to the nanofluid being studied and can be used across certain nanofluid kinds, volume fraction, and Re number ranges. One way to characterize the generic equation is:

$$Nu = A Re^x Pr^y \phi^z \tag{28}$$

Where each author determines the constants A, x, y, and z for the particular situation they discuss. When the correlation holds true for the base fluid as well (when $\phi = 0$), the term $(1 + \phi)$ may show up.

The study's numerical data were used to create two correlations, The Nusselt number's newly discovered correlation of Al₂O₃-water nanofluid ($\phi = 0.03$) in a triangular channel displayed as follows:

$$Nu = 0.9675 Re^{0.6585} Pr^{3.8812} \phi^{2.2054} \tag{29}$$

And The Nusselt number's newly discovered correlation of Al₂O₃-SiO₂-water (10:90) hybrid nanofluid ($\phi = 0.03$) in a triangular channel provided as follows:

$$Nu = 0.9664 Re^{0.6496} Pr^{3.8498} \phi^{2.2199} \tag{30}$$

VI. CONCLUSION

In this article, a test was made to study the performance of corrugations and hybrid nanofluids and mono nanofluids on the intensification of heat transfer by forced convection. The results showed that:

- 1- Confidence in the numerical model's performance was guaranteed by a high degree of consistency between the experimental and numerical model results.
- 2- For both mono and hybrid nanofluids, as well as hybrid nanofluids, the Nusselt number rises as the Reynolds number does; on the other hand, the coefficient of friction decreases each time the Reynolds number increases.
- 3- A great class of fluids for improving convective heat transfer is hybrid nanofluids.
- 4- In terms of convective transfer, the hybrid nanofluid with the percentage ratio (10:90) exhibits the best performance, whereas the hybrid nanofluid with the percentage ratio (50:50) exhibits the lowest performance.
- 5- There is no distinction in the coefficient of friction between mono and hybrid nanofluids.
- 6- When the Reynolds number rises, the entropy resulting from heat transfer, the total entropy and the Bejan number decreases; conversely, the entropy due to viscous increases.
- 7- The pressure drop is higher for hybrid nanofluids than for mono nanofluids.
- 8- Two correlations were established using the investigation's numerical results.

Abbreviations

<i>Symbols</i>		RNG	Renormalized group k-ε model
a	corrugated channel amplitude, (mm)	S	area (m ²)
Al ₂ O ₃	alumina	SIMPLE	Semi-implicit method for pressure-linked equations
Ag	Silver	SiO ₂	silicon dioxide
C _p	specific heat, (J/kg K)	S ^{'''} _g	local volumetric entropy generation (W/m ³ K)
CuO	copper oxide	T	Input temperature, (K)
Cu	copper	T ₀	reference temperature, (T ₀ = 273 k)
C _ε	turbulent model constant	TiO ₂	Titanium dioxide
Cu	copper	u	component of velocity in the x direction, (m/s)
CFD	computational fluid dynamic	v	component of velocity in the y direction, (m/s)
C _ε	turbulent model constant	ZnO	zinc oxide
D _h	hydraulic diameter, (mm)		

d_p	nanofluid particles' diameter (nm)		
d_f	equal diameter of a base fluid molecule		
EG	ethylene glycol	<i>Subscript</i>	
f	friction factor		
Gk	production rate of the kinetic energy of turbulence.	c	corrugated channel
H	channel's height, (mm)	eff	effective particles
h	heat transfer coefficient, (W/m ² K)	p	base fluid
I	turbulent intensity	f	nanofluid
K	thermal conductivity, (W/ m K)	nf	nanofluid
k	turbulent kinetic energy	hnf	hybrid nanofluid
K_t	turbulent thermal conductivity	<i>Dimensionless</i>	
L	corrugated channel length,(mm)	<i>numbers</i>	
L_w	wave length of corrugated channel,(mm)	Re	Reynolds number
M	base fluid molecular weight	Nu	Nusselt number
N	Number of Avogadro = 6.022×10^{-23} mol ⁻¹	Be	Bejan number
n	factor of empirical form	Pr	prandtl number
Δp	pressure drop, (Pa)	Pr_t	turbulent prandtl number
P	pressure, (Pa)		
P_w	wet perimeter, (mm)		

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